

MICROBE
the Microbiome
Biobanking (RI)
Enabler

MICROBE paves the way for innovative microbiome biobanking in Europe by combining scientific expertise with research infrastructures know-how.

Biobanking of complex microbiome samples has been initiated in the human healthcare sector, for example, by initiatives such as the Microbiota Vault Project (www.microbiotavault.org/) or the Global Microbiome Conservancy initiative (www.microbiomeconservancy.org/), but across other biological domains research infrastructures currently lack optimised methodologies and technologies to preserve and provide access to microbiome samples and massive amounts of associated data. The most significant technological bottleneck is the development of optimised methodologies for the preservation of microbiomes and for assessing the success of preservation in maintaining their composition and functionality. There is also an imminent need for the establishment of a unified data infrastructure to support microbiome research and innovation, as well as the implementation of standardisation across sectors.

MICROBE focuses on developing technical methods for preservation, isolation, co-cultivation and functionality assessment, novel ecological concepts and data infrastructures. Besides assessing the applicability of the technological solutions, MICROBE will also work on ethical and legal requirements and develop new business models. MICROBE cooperates with relevant European research infrastructures, BBMRI-ERIC, MIRRI, ELIXIR and EMBRC-ERIC, to ensure the validation and uptake of project results into practice.

Project data:

- › Duration: 02/2023 – 01/2027
- › EU Funding: € 5,804,683.00
- › www.microbiomeproject.eu

Project Outcomes:

- › Validated protocols for preservation, isolation and co-cultivation of complex microbiome samples
- › Novel isolates representative of key microbiome members from different domains
- › Novel synthetic consortia reproducing the key functionalities of selected ecosystems
- › Customised data infrastructure tools for microbiome biobanking
- › Guidelines for implementation of standardised microbiome biobanking workflows in selected fields
- › Guidelines for establishment of ethical and legal framework conditions that enable microbiome biobanking
- › Business models for the implementation and exploitation of novel microbiome-based technologies and resources
- › Portfolio of training and educational resources

